

M3C2 Tool

Analysis Report

CHECKPOINT 13

Point Cloud Change Detection · M3C2 Algorithm

py4dgeo · laspy · NumPy · SciPy · matplotlib

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Processing time	10 min 32 s
Version	CHECKPOINT 13
GitHub	github.com/Kostka22/Geology_M3C2-from-point-cloud

1. System Information

Parameter	Value
Operating System	Windows 10
Python	3.11.9
Architecture	AMD64
CPU	Intel64 Family 6 Model 158 Stepping 10, GenuineIntel
CPU Cores	6 physical / 12 logical
CPU Frequency	2592 MHz (max 2592 MHz)
RAM Total	15.9 GB
RAM Available	5.8 GB
GPU	NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2060 (6.0 GB) driver 581.83

2. Input Data

Reference Cloud (Epoch 1)

Property	Value
File name	MB1_vyrez.laz
Full path	D:/DIPLOMOVKA/TEST_DATA_Kykula/MB1_vyrez.laz
File size	6.66 MB
Point count	2,060,704
X range	-506753.53 – -506269.82 m
Y range	-1199334.45 – -1199070.72 m
Z range	528.83 – 630.84 m

Comparison Cloud (Epoch 2)

Property	Value
File name	MB2_vyrez.laz
Full path	D:/DIPLOMOVKA/TEST_DATA_Kykula/MB2_vyrez.laz
File size	9.79 MB
Point count	3,359,228
X range	-506753.71 – -506269.82 m
Y range	-1199334.44 – -1199070.76 m
Z range	528.72 – 630.78 m

3. Processing Parameters

Parameter	Value	Notes
Computation engine	py4dgeo	py4dgeo = per-point LoD; PDAL = OpenMP multi-core
Cylinder radius	2.5 m	Radius of projection cylinder
Normal radii	[1.5, 2.0, 3.0]	Multi-scale normal estimation
Corepoint spacing	0.25 m greedy distance filter	Spatial subsampling
Max depth filter	Disabled	Outlier distance threshold
Confidence level	95 %	Significance test threshold
Sigma mode	Automatic (from py4dgeo SPREAD1/SPREAD2)	
Sigma 1	0.0676 m	Epoch 1 position uncertainty
Sigma 2	0.0981 m	Epoch 2 position uncertainty
Level of Detection	0.2335 m	$t \times \sqrt{\sigma_{\pm}^2 + \sigma^2}$
Raster resolution	0.25 m	
Raster interpolation	Nearest	
DEM resolution	0.25 m	
Quiver export	Normal-direction	Grid cell: 5.0 m

4. M3C2 Algorithm – How It Works

The **Multiscale Model to Model Cloud Comparison (M3C2)** algorithm (Lague, Brodu & Leroux, 2013) computes signed 3-D distances between two point clouds directly along the local surface normal. Unlike raster DoD, M3C2 works on any surface orientation – flat terrain, steep slopes, vertical faces, and overhangs.

1 — Normal estimation

At each corepoint a plane is fitted to the k nearest neighbours across multiple scales (the Normal radii list). The scale that minimises local roughness is automatically selected per point.

2 — Projection cylinder

A cylinder of radius r (Cylinder radius) is projected along the normal. All points from both clouds that fall inside are collected.

3 — M3C2 distance

The mean position of each cloud inside the cylinder is computed. The signed distance along the normal between those two means is the M3C2 distance d. Positive = surface moved away from the reference; negative = surface moved toward it.

4 — Uncertainty (Level of Detection)

The LoD combines point cloud roughness (SPREAD1, SPREAD2) and registration error (sigma). A change is flagged significant only if $|d| > t \times \sqrt{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2}$.

5 — Displacement components

$D_X = d \times n_x$, $D_Y = d \times n_y$, $D_Z = d \times n_z$ decompose the M3C2 distance onto the Cartesian axes of the unit normal vector, giving physically interpretable east, north, and vertical components.

Significance test:

$$|\text{M3C2 distance}| > t_{\text{critical}} \times \sqrt{\sigma_1^2 + \sigma_2^2}$$

Confidence Level	t-critical	Interpretation
90 %	1.645	Less conservative
95 %	1.960	Standard (default)
99 %	2.576	Most conservative

Reference: Lague, D., Brodu, N., Leroux, J. (2013). Accurate 3D comparison of complex topography with terrestrial laser scanner: Application to the Rangitikei canyon (N-Z). *ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing*, 82, 10–26.

5. Results Statistics

5.1 Overview

Metric	Value
Total corepoints	794,162
Valid corepoints	792,071
Invalid (NaN / filtered)	2,091
Significant changes	154,284 (19.5 %)
Not significant	637,787 (80.5 %)
Level of Detection (LoD)	0.2335 m
Confidence level	95 %
Sigma 1	0.0676 m
Sigma 2	0.0981 m

5.2 Distance Statistics

Statistic	All valid	Significant only
Minimum	-2.6168 m	-2.6168 m
Maximum	2.7516 m	2.7516 m
Mean	-0.0427 m	-0.0320 m
Median	-0.0456 m	-0.2489 m
Std Dev	0.5056 m	1.1423 m
RMS	0.5074 m	1.1428 m

5.3 Change Magnitude Distribution

Range	Count	% of valid	Cumulative %
< 0.10 m	595,213	75.1 %	75.1 %
0.10–0.25 m	45,224	5.7 %	80.9 %
0.25–0.50 m	32,468	4.1 %	85.0 %
0.50–1.00 m	55,633	7.0 %	92.0 %
1.00–2.00 m	52,225	6.6 %	98.6 %
2.00–5.00 m	11,308	1.4 %	100.0 %
5.00–10.0 m	0	0.0 %	100.0 %
> 10.0 m	0	0.0 %	100.0 %

5.4 Normal Vector & Displacement Components

Field	Min	Max	Mean	Description
Nz	0.008	1.000	0.958	1.0=horizontal, 0.0=vertical

Nxy	0.000	1.000	0.252	0.0=horizontal, 1.0=vertical
DX	-1.6083	1.8714	-0.0020	East displacement [m]
DY	-1.5207	1.4637	-0.0040	North displacement [m]
DZ	-2.5604	2.6337	-0.0343	Vertical displacement [m]

5.5 Surface Change Classification

Significant changes split into erosion (negative M3C2) and deposition (positive M3C2) classes. Areas estimated as $n_points \times cell_size^2$ using the raster resolution parameter.

Class	Points	Est. area	Mean dist	Median dist	Min dist	Max dist
Erosion (loss)	78,680	4,917.50 m ²	-1.0031 m	-0.8749 m	-2.6168 m	-0.2335 m
Deposition (gain)	75,604	4,725.25 m ²	0.9786 m	0.8459 m	0.2335 m	2.7516 m
Total significant	154,284	9,642.75 m ²	-0.0320 m	-0.2489 m	-2.6168 m	2.7516 m

Deposition / erosion point ratio: 0.96 (— net erosion dominant)

6. M3C2 Distance Histogram

Grey bars = all valid corepoints. Blue = significant negative changes (surface loss). Red = significant positive changes (surface gain). Dashed lines = \pm Level of Detection. Shaded band = below LoD zone.

Figure. vystup_histogram.png

7. Volume Change Estimation

Two DoD methods computed using the same interpolated raster. Both clouds are thinned to one point per grid cell before interpolation for speed, then subtracted cell by cell.

Method A — DoD all cells

Both clouds rasterised to a 0.25 m grid (Nearest). $dZ = Z_{\text{new}} - Z_{\text{old}}$. All non-NaN cells contribute. Comparable to CloudCompare's Compute 2.5D Volume.

Method B — DoD significant cells only

Same raster as Method A. Only cells where $|dZ| > \text{LoD}$ (0.2335 m) contribute. Removes sub-noise cells — DoD equivalent of the M3C2 significance filter.

Results Comparison

Metric	DoD all cells	DoD sig cells only
Volume gain (+)	+11590.824 m ³	+11039.608 m ³
Volume loss (-)	-15157.152 m ³	-10975.399 m ³
Net volume change	-3566.328 m ³	+64.209 m ³
Grid cells used	1,617,918	319,206
LoD threshold	none	$ dZ > 0.2335 \text{ m}$

Difference between methods: 200.0 % — large discrepancy.

Interpretation: Method A is comparable to CloudCompare's Compute 2.5D Volume. Method B removes sub-noise cells using the same LoD threshold as the M3C2 significance test. A small difference between methods means most volume change is real signal.

8. Profile Location Map

Top-down overview of all M3C2 corepoints. Grey = not significant. Coloured = significant (RdBu_r scale). Orange-red lines and shaded bands mark the profile corridor locations.

Figure 1. M3C2 overview with 5 profile line(s).

Profile Lines

#	Label	Start (X, Y)	End (X, Y)	Length [m]	Corridor
1	Line 1	(-506698.0, -1199147.0)	(-506347.9, -1199094.3)	354.11	±1.2 m
2	Line 2	(-506747.0, -1199216.1)	(-506309.8, -1199124.7)	446.60	±1.2 m
3	Line 3	(-506743.7, -1199249.2)	(-506288.1, -1199163.9)	463.57	±1.2 m
4	Line 4	(-506743.2, -1199289.5)	(-506281.5, -1199193.8)	471.44	±1.2 m
5	Line 5	(-506704.0, -1199283.0)	(-506415.3, -1199076.9)	354.72	±1.2 m

9. Profile Cross-Sections

Upper panel: reference cloud (blue) and comparison cloud (red) projected into the profile corridor. Lower panel: M3C2 distance with \pm LoD threshold lines. Grey points = not significant; coloured = significant.

Profile length: 446.60 m · corridor ± 1.2 m · ref: 5,132 pts · comp: 5,087 pts · M3C2 Tool - CHECKPOINT13

Start: (-506747.0, -1199216.1) End: (-506309.8, -1199124.7)

Figure 2. vystup_profile_02.png

Profile length: 354.11 m · corridor ± 1.2 m · ref: 4,330 pts · comp: 4,404 pts · M3C2 Tool - CHECKPOINT13

Start: (-506698.0, -1199147.0) End: (-506347.9, -1199094.3)

Figure 3. vystup_profile_01.png

Profile length: 354.72 m · corridor ± 1.2 m · ref: 3,816 pts · comp: 3,794 pts · M3C2 Tool - CHECKPOINT13

Start: (-506704.0, -1199283.0) End: (-506415.3, -1199076.9)

Figure 4. *vystup_profile_05.png*

Profile length: 463.57 m · corridor ± 1.2 m · ref: 5,932 pts · comp: 5,426 pts · M3C2 Tool - CHECKPOINT13

Start: (-506743.7, -1199249.2) End: (-506288.1, -1199163.9)

Figure 5. *vystup_profile_03.png*

Profile length: 471.44 m · corridor ± 1.2 m · ref: 6,022 pts · comp: 5,523 pts · M3C2 Tool - CHECKPOINT13

Start: (-506743.2, -1199289.5) End: (-506281.5, -1199193.8)

Figure 6. *vystup_profile_04.png*

10. Wind Rose – Displacement Direction & Magnitude

Panel (a): horizontal azimuth rose (0° = North, clockwise). Panel (b): vertical angle from horizontal. Four exports: all points (grey = not significant, coloured = significant), all significant only, positive changes only (gain / deposition), negative changes only (loss / erosion).

Figure. All points – grey = not significant, coloured = significant (vystup_windrose.png)

Figure. All significant changes only (vystup_windrose_sig.png)

M3C2 Wind Rose : positive changes only (deposition / gain) · 73,624 points · 32 azimuth bins

b) Vertical movement angle

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Figure. Positive changes only (gain / deposition) (vystup_windrose_pos.png)

M3C2 Wind Rose : negative changes only (erosion / loss) · 80,660 points · 32 azimuth bins

b) Vertical movement angle

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Figure. Negative changes only (loss / erosion) (vystup_windrose_neg.png)

11. Output Files

File name	Size	Description
vystup.laz	21.96 MB	Corepoint cloud with M3C2 scalar fields (LAZ)
vystup_DX.tif	7.81 MB	GeoTIFF – X displacement component
vystup_SIGNIFICANT.tif	7.81 MB	GeoTIFF – significance flag (1/0)
vystup_SPREAD2.tif	7.81 MB	GeoTIFF – Epoch 2 roughness
vystup_LOD.tif	7.81 MB	GeoTIFF – Level of Detection
vystup_Nz.tif	7.81 MB	GeoTIFF – normal Z component
vystup_DZ.tif	7.81 MB	GeoTIFF – Z displacement component
vystup_SPREAD1.tif	7.81 MB	GeoTIFF – Epoch 1 roughness
vystup_M3C2_DISTANCE.tif	7.81 MB	GeoTIFF – M3C2 signed distance
vystup_DY.tif	7.81 MB	GeoTIFF – Y displacement component
vystup_Nxy.tif	7.81 MB	GeoTIFF – normal XY magnitude
vystup_DEM.tif	7.81 MB	GeoTIFF – Digital Elevation Model
vystup_quiver_normal.png	233 KB	Quiver PNG – normal-direction
vystup_quiver_normal.html	712 KB	Quiver interactive HTML – normal-direction
vystup_quiver_normal.gpkg	944 KB	Quiver GPKG – normal-direction arrows
vystup_profile_02.png	198 KB	Profile cross-section PNG
vystup_profile_01.png	187 KB	Profile cross-section PNG
vystup_profile_05.png	253 KB	Profile cross-section PNG
vystup_profile_03.png	203 KB	Profile cross-section PNG
vystup_profile_04.png	185 KB	Profile cross-section PNG
vystup_profiles.txt	1 KB	Profile line trajectories – reloadable into tool
vystup_windrose.png	249 KB	Wind rose – all points (grey + coloured)
vystup_windrose_sig.png	309 KB	Wind rose – all significant changes only
vystup_windrose_pos.png	250 KB	Wind rose – positive changes only (gain / deposition)
vystup_windrose_neg.png	259 KB	Wind rose – negative changes only (loss / erosion)
vystup_histogram.png	76 KB	M3C2 distance histogram PNG

M3C2 Tool – CHECKPOINT 13 – Samuel Lebo – github.com/Kostka22/Geology_M3C2-from-point-cloud